

New records of *Centrotus cornutus* (LINNAEUS, 1758) (Hemiptera: Membracidae) from Poland

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ABSTRACT. New records of *Centrotus cornutus* (LINNAEUS, 1758) (Hemiptera: Membracidae) from Poland.

Thorn hopper *Centrotus cornutus* (L.) is commonly known member of Membracidae: Cicadomorpha: Hemiptera, but collected in low numbers, with most of the records from southern and central parts of Poland. Here new records of this treehopper are presented from Baltic Coast, Mazovian Lowland, Eastern and Pomeranian Lakelands, respectively.

KEY WORDS: faunistics, new records, treehoppers, Cicadomorpha, distribution, Poland.

The family Membracidae (Hemiptera: Cicadomorpha), commonly known as treehoppers, is represented in Europe by five species: *Gargara genistae* (FABRICIUS, 1775), *Centrotus chloroticus* FAIRMAIRE, 1851, *Centrotus cornutus* (LINNAEUS, 1758) and *Oxyrhachis capeneri* IZZARD, 1953 (nec *Oxyrhachis delelandei* FAIRMAIRE, 1846: 268; = *Oxyrhachis delalandei*: FIEBER 1876: 13 [3]) and introduced North American species *Stictocephala bisonia* KOPP et YONKE, 1977 (NAST 1987, MCKAMEY 1998, ŚWIERCZEWSKI & STROIŃSKI 2011).

The genus *Centrotus* FABRICIUS, 1803 (Centrotinae, Centrotini) comprises 21 species, distributed in Afrotropical, Palearctic, Indomalayan, and Australian regions and also introduced to the Nearctic region. There are several species from this genus occurring in different region of Europe for example *Centrotus chloroticus* is present in France, Spain and Portugal (NAST 1987), while *Centrotus cornutus* is present in the Western Palearctic region east to the Kazakhstan and in the north of the Saharo-Arabian region (NAST 1972, 1987; DMITRIEV 2019). This species occurs in moderately moist to dry sites with tall herbs or shrubs, usually along woodland margins and among herb stands in dry grassland, along hedges, forest roads and margins, along shores, as well as in the interior of open forests with luxuriant undergrowth (HOLZINGER *et al.* 2003, NICKEL 2003). It is active between May to October; semivoltine species, with nymphs usually staying near the base of the host plant (mainly *Vincetoxicum*, *Cirsium*, *Carduus* and *Urtica*), adults ascend to the upper herb and shrub layer for feeding and oviposition and are often swept from low-growing woody plants (*Populus*, *Quercus*, *Rubus*, *Prunus* and others) (HOLZINGER *et al.* 2003, NICKEL 2003). The habitus of the species both as nymph and imago is very

Fig. 1. *C. cornutus* (L.). (Photo Mateusz Sowiński, swiatmakro.com; used with permission).

Ryc. 1. *C. cornutus* (L.). (fot. Mateusz Sowiński, swiatmakro.com; za zgodą autora).

Fig. 2. *C. cornutus* (L.). (Photo Mateusz Sowiński, swiatmakro.com; used with permission).

Ryc. 2. *C. cornutus* (L.). (fot. Mateusz Sowiński, swiatmakro.com; za zgodą autora).

characteristic (Figs. 1, 2), with a robust body, strongly convex pronotum, on each side with a triangular pointed process and caudally with a slender, weakly curved, dorsally sharply carinate process, extending almost to apex of the abdomen; with wings longer than the abdomen and roof-like covering it, translucent, with brownish veins and fuscous spot on the hind border a little distally of the claval apex; yellowish brown legs, with hind tibiae short, equipped with fine, setigerous tubercles.

In Poland, it seems to be relatively often, but collected in low numbers, with most of the records from southern and central parts of the country (NAST 1976, GĘBICKI *et al.* 2013, MARCZAK 2021) (Fig. 3). The species was not reported in the Baltic Coast region since WAGNER (1941).

During the faunistic research, the species was found in following localities:

Gdańsk-Oliwa, VII Dwór (Seventh Manor House), Green Valey, the forest's edge, ecotone, one individual, leg. and det. B. Bieszczad, 54.39 N, 18.56 E, UTM CF42, 25.05.2018, Baltic Coast;

Gdynia, "Arka Gdynia" club city stadium, leg. and det. J.K. Kowalczyk, 54.49 N, 18.53 E, UTM CF34, 1-16.07.2014, Baltic Coast.

During the search for the data on the species unpublished records at insectarium.net, iNaturalist.com and swiatmakro.com additional reports were found. After contacting the authors of these observations, we obtained consent to include them in this paper:

Gdańsk, Tricity Landscape Park (Trójmiejski Park Krajobrazowy), 2 specimens, leg. and det. Bogdan Mazur, 54.21 N, 18.31 E, UTM CF34, Baltic Coast;

Kartuzy, 2 specimens, leg. and det. Bill Lucas, 54.41 N, 18.44 E, UTM WGS84, 11.06.2013, Pomeranian Lakelands;

Struga Dobieszkowska, leg. and det. A. Kucharski, 51.85 N, 19.59 E, UTM DC04, 02.06.2013, Mazovian Lowland;

Uherce Mineralne, leg. and det. A. Kucharski, 49.46 N 22.40 E, UTM FV08, 27.05.2019, Eastern Carpathians;

Dajtki, Olsztyn, leg. and det. M. Sowiński, 53.78 N, 20.41 E, UTM DE65, 19.06.2017, Eastern Lakelands;

Kortowo, Olsztyn, leg. and det. M. Sowiński, 53.75 N, 20.44 E, UTM DE65, 30.05.2013, Eastern Lakelands;

Kudyby, Olsztyn, leg. and det. M. Sowiński, 53.76 N, 20.378 E, UTM DE55, 23.04.2015, Eastern Lakelands.

Centrotus cornutus is a quite commonly occurring treehopper in Poland. It seems to be a rare species because it is rarely recorded. This species is present in most of Europe, in the eastern Palaearctic realm and in the Near East (FAUNA EUROPAEA 2017, GBIF 2021). This work gives new records of the occurrence of *C. cornutus* found in Poland on the Baltic coast area, Eastern Lakelands, Eastern Carpathians and Mazovian Lowland. This treehopper is a charismatic species that can say a lot about the environment in which it was found. The occurrence records of this species may contribute to the protection of areas inhabited by it as well as by other less striking visually species of great ecological importance. This is why research on entomofauna is so important to get to know the areas and habitats better and to protect them.

Fig. 3. Map of Poland with current records of *C. cornutus* (L.). Source: biomap.pl.

Ryc. 3. Mapa Polski z aktualnymi stwierdzeniami *C. cornutus* (L.). Źródło: biomap.pl.

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Streszczenie

Nowe stwierdzenia *Centrotus cornutus* (LINNAEUS, 1758) (Hemiptera: Membracidae) w Polsce

Zgarb rogaty *Centrotus cornutus* (L.) jest powszechnie znanym przedstawicielem Membracidae: Cicadomorpha: Hemiptera, lecz zbieranym nielicznie, przy czym większość stwierdzeń pochodzi z południowej i środkowej Polski. Praca prezentuje nowe dane na temat tego gatunku z Pobrzeża Bałtyku, Niziny Mazowieckiej, Pojezierza Wschodniego i Pojezierza Pomorskiego.

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